

**MORE THAN JUST A RESIDENCY AT A SMALL HEALTH POST:
AN EXPERIENCE REPORT**

MÁS QUE UNA RESIDENCIA EN UN PUESTO DE SALUD: UN RELATO DE EXPERIENCIA

MAIS QUE UMA RESIDÊNCIA NUM POSTINHO DE SAÚDE: UM RELATO DE
EXPERIÊNCIA

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Abstract

Multiprofessional Residency Programs in Family Health (RMSF) are an essential strategy for the training and qualification of professionals within the Unified Health System (SUS). This report aims to describe the experience and training of a physical therapist resident within the Multiprofessional RMSF in a municipality in eastern Minas Gerais. This qualitative experience report draws upon the lived experience of a physical therapist resident in the RMSF. It explores the practices developed in Family Health units in eastern Minas Gerais, Brazil, emphasizing the interaction among multiprofessional team members, the challenges encountered, and the experience's impact on professional development. The RMSF demonstrated significant potential in expanding the scope of physical therapists' practice, fostering networking, and promoting the development of more comprehensive care. However, obstacles such as resistance to the implementation of rehabilitation actions, the organization of operational groups, limited political recognition of the program, inadequate municipal management, and deficient physical infrastructure have hindered the effectiveness of the proposed actions. Despite these obstacles, the RMSF emerges as a promising strategy for physical therapist training in Primary Health Care, though it requires improvements in its organization, recognition, and infrastructure. Continued investment in training and improved policy planning are essential to overcoming these obstacles and fulfilling its transformative potential for health education and enhancing care for the population it serves.

Keywords: Primary Health Care; Physiotherapy; Family Health.

Resumen

Los Programas de Residencia Multiprofesional en Salud de la Familia (RMSF) son una estrategia esencial para la formación de profesionales en el Sistema Único de Salud (SUS). Por lo tanto, el objetivo es relatar la experiencia y formación de un fisioterapeuta residente en el Programa RMSF en un municipio del este de Minas Gerais. Se trata de un relato de experiencia con un

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enfoque cualitativo, basado en la práctica de un fisioterapeuta residente en el RMSF. El estudio explora las acciones desarrolladas en unidades de Salud de la Familia del este de Minas Gerais, Brasil, con énfasis en la interacción del equipo multiprofesional, los desafíos enfrentados y el impacto en el desarrollo profesional. El RMSF ha demostrado ser eficaz para ampliar el trabajo de los fisioterapeutas, fomentar redes y una atención más integral. Sin embargo, obstáculos como la resistencia a implementar acciones de rehabilitación, la organización de grupos operativos, el bajo reconocimiento político del programa, la débil gestión municipal y la infraestructura deficiente han limitado la efectividad de las acciones. A pesar de estos obstáculos, el RMSF se presenta como una estrategia prometedora para la formación de fisioterapeutas en Atención Primaria de Salud, pero requiere mejoras en su organización, reconocimiento e infraestructura. La inversión continua en formación y mejor planificación política son esenciales para superar estos desafíos y materializar su potencial transformador en la educación para la salud y la atención a la población que atiende.

Palabras clave: Atención Primaria de Salud; Fisioterapia; Salud Familiar.

Resumo

Os Programas de Residência Multiprofissional em Saúde da Família (RMSF) são uma estratégia essencial para a formação de profissionais do Sistema Único de Saúde (SUS). Dessa forma, tem-se como objetivo relatar a vivência e formação da fisioterapeuta residente no Programa de RMSF de um município do leste mineiro. Trata-se de um relato de experiência com abordagem qualitativa, baseado na vivência de uma fisioterapeuta residente na RMSF. O estudo explora as práticas desenvolvidas nas unidades de Saúde da Família do leste de Minas Gerais, Brasil, com ênfase na interação entre os membros da equipe multiprofissional, nos desafios enfrentados e no impacto da experiência na formação profissional. A RMSF revelou-se potente para ampliar o campo de atuação da fisioterapeuta, favorecendo o trabalho em rede e a construção de um cuidado mais integral. No entanto, obstáculos como a resistência à implementação de ações de reabilitação, a organização de grupos operacionais, a baixa valorização política do programa, a gestão municipal fragilizada e a estrutura física deficiente dificultaram a eficácia das ações propostas. Apesar dos entraves, a RMSF se apresenta como uma estratégia promissora para a formação da fisioterapeuta na Atenção Primária à Saúde, mas exige melhorias em sua organização, valorização e infraestrutura. Investimentos contínuos em capacitação e um melhor planejamento político são essenciais para a superação dos obstáculos e para a efetivação de seu potencial transformador na formação em saúde e na melhoria da atenção à população assistida.

Palavras-chave: Atenção Primária à Saúde; Fisioterapia; Saúde da Família.

Introduction

Established by the Ministry of Health (MS) through Law No. 11,129, of June 30, 2005, Multiprofessional Residency Programs in Health (RMS) constitute a *latu sensu* postgraduate education modality aimed at health professionals, excluding physicians (Brasil, 2006). The program seeks to train professionals to operate distinctly within the Unified Health System (SUS), emphasizing interdisciplinary development, teamwork, continuing education, and the reorientation of techno-assistive approaches (Brasil, 2012).

The RMS requires pedagogical strategies for its guidance and organization. These strategies are crucial for leveraging and providing learning scenarios rooted in the care pathways of Health Care Networks (RAS). By adopting methodologies and mechanisms of expanded clinical management, the RMS ensures training grounded in comprehensive, multiprofessional, and interdisciplinary care (Brasil, 2012).

In the context of Primary Health Care (PHC), there is a perceived need for specialists who can manage common daily situations, being effective, assertive, and capable of mitigating less complex health conditions that might otherwise overburden other levels of care within the network. This is because PHC still poses challenges in terms of management, financing, expansion, and the improvement of work processes for both management and care delivery. In this context, Family Health Residencies present themselves as a crucial ally to overcome these challenges and gaps in the Brazilian reality (Carvalho; Gutiérrez, 2021).

Among the professionals working in Family Health Residencies, the physiotherapist is essential due to their broad scope of practice. Emphasizing this scope, Bill No. 1,111/2019 mandates the inclusion of physiotherapists in Family Health Strategy (ESF) teams. Physiotherapists perform specific assessments, assist in the control of neurological disorders, prevent injuries, conduct rehabilitation, and help restore movement and address functional limitations. These comprehensive actions promote citizen well-being and ensure the integration of prevention and health promotion. To that end, this study aims to report the experience and training of a physical therapist resident in the Multiprofessional Residency Program in Family Health of a municipality in eastern Minas Gerais.

Methods

This study presents an experience report (Mussi; Flores; Almeida, 2021) detailing the professional journey of a resident physiotherapist within the Multiprofessional Residency Program in Family Health in Governador Valadares, Minas Gerais, Brazil, from 2022 to 2024. The narrative draws upon lived experiences and records maintained in a critical-reflective portfolio. This portfolio, an assessment tool proposed by the coordination of the Multiprofessional Residency Commission in Health (COREMU), facilitated the documentation and reflection on the training trajectory.

The residency commenced in March 2022, with the resident's integration into a multiprofessional team. This team comprised resident professionals from the fields of physiotherapy, nutrition, physical education, nursing, pharmacy, psychology, social work, and dentistry. As this report relies exclusively on the portfolio, submission to the Human Research Ethics Committee was deemed unnecessary.

Initially, the resident's practice was conducted in six ESF units, alongside the former Expanded Family Health and Primary Care Centers (NASF-AB) that covered these ESF areas. Throughout the training, however, the resident was reallocated to other practical settings in response to local needs. This dynamic fostered a comprehensive experience in PHC, providing exposure to diverse scenarios and their specificities. Such a varied trajectory prompted self-reflection, thereby enriching the training process and strengthening a critical understanding of her role as a resident in PHC.

This report details the resident's professional experience, derived from her multiprofessional work within the teams and the construction of the critical-reflective portfolio. It highlights reflections and impressions concerning the resident's developmental process. The information presented predominantly stems from individual observations and records compiled throughout this experience.

Results

Over the two years of the Residency, practice in PHC was conducted across three multiprofessional teams, with each team operating in six health units. Each unit presented unique characteristics in terms of physical infrastructure, human resources, material resources, location, catchment population, community participation, and its understanding of the residency's role and physiotherapeutic practice.

Integration into the practical setting involved exposing the resident to each unit's work processes, including their facilitators and barriers, and their population and community profiles. Based on a situational diagnosis, the health unit, its coverage area, and population were mapped and described.

Activities performed encompassed individual, collective, educational, and social initiatives, reflecting the comprehensive nature of primary care. Typically, the physiotherapist's practice included operative groups (GOs), individual and co-managed

appointments, home visits and care, participation in the School Health Program (PSE), general and specific guidance, social mobilization, health education, and continuing and permanent education for professionals within the unit and the broader basic care network.

GOs functioned as a demand-driven strategy. Participant mobilization was facilitated by resources available in PHC, particularly within health units. Strategies such as engaging patients in waiting rooms, inviting them during existing group meetings, and promotion by local management via digital channels were utilized.

Regarding the GOs, they were conducted twice weekly for groups sharing a common objective, predominantly women over 40 with sedentary lifestyles. Sessions were conducted for one hour at 8 AM in the mornings. These sessions took place in outdoor areas of the health units or in public spaces like squares, churchyards, and sports courts, offering physical exercises, physiotherapeutic guidance, and health advice.

Conducting the GOs in outdoor and public spaces presented several challenges. These included the influence of weather conditions, venue availability (conflict of use), access and mobility issues, noise and distractions, and inadequate infrastructure maintenance. Such conditions also hampered the transportation of materials and equipment required for activities.

Autonomy was granted to residents to create new groups, depending on local needs and population acceptance. Consequently, groups such as the Low Back Pain Prevention Group, the Shoulder Pain Prevention Group (Group: A Friendly Shoulder), and the Cognitive Stimulation Group were initiated. The Cognitive Stimulation Group specifically aimed to enhance users' cognitive function through activities focusing on concentration, reasoning, memory, and attention. Moreover, health education activities within these groups addressed themes relevant to the population's needs, facilitating knowledge sharing and fostering health ownership.

Health education activities were structured based on the annual health calendar, which guided the execution of activities related to monthly commemorative dates. The themes addressed often reflected recurring demands and needs from both health services and the community, with which they identified.

Beyond immediate local needs, professionals also played an active role in proposing topics considered relevant for health promotion, even when not directly requested by users. Consequently, themes emerged from a balance between addressing population needs and leveraging professional initiative, with the goal of expanding access to information and strengthening comprehensive health care.

Individual activities conducted at the health units originated from spontaneous demand, internal interprofessional communication (especially from Community Health Agents - CHAs), and medical referrals. The resident organized her own schedule for appointments and follow-ups, as well as the frequency and duration of longitudinal care. Nevertheless, the health units lacked available physiotherapeutic materials, requiring the creation and improvisation of resources for clinical cases. Frequently, the resident utilized personal materials, such as elastic bands, mini bands, dumbbells, and ankle weights.

Home visits and care were typically conducted with another professional from the health unit or a multiprofessional team from a different specialty. Requests for visits originated from family members, CHAs, or other professionals, aiming to comprehensively understand the patient's reality across physical, familial, financial, emotional, structural, and social dimensions. Consequently, health and physiotherapeutic guidance, ergonomic adaptations, harm reduction, rehabilitation, and continuous follow-up were provided. These activities prioritized bedridden and homebound individuals, and those with difficulty accessing the health unit.

The PSE actions, across all dimensions, were integrated into the school's political-pedagogical project, considering the reality of each territory, and the autonomy of educators and pedagogical teams. Themes addressed in the PSE were selected and structured through discussions about the local reality of the school and the community; however, pre-established themes from the Ministry of Health and Education were also developed. Furthermore, themes were aligned with the students' reality, and when a problematic issue was identified in that environment, it became the focus of discussions. The PSE was carried out with students from the municipal public school system, and professionals developed actions monthly, with the teaching methodology determined at their discretion.

Matrix support was integrated into the health units, generally occurring in the first full week of each month, as per the teams' organization. The Singular Therapeutic Project (PTS) was also implemented, with meetings typically recorded in minutes.

During the resident physiotherapist's experience, it was observed that, in practice, many of these meetings diverged from recommendations for matrix support. These meetings were often configured more as a response to institutional goals rather than as spaces for collective and qualified care construction. This configuration largely reflected weaknesses in the support network among professionals, the absence of full team participation, reduced meeting time, and a lack of specific planning for this moment.

Concerning the implementation of the PTS, it was observed that, in several cases, this instrument was utilized with limited commitment, sometimes being limited to the repetition of standardized procedures, which diluted its problem-solving potential. Despite matrix support and the PTS being fundamental strategies for strengthening SUS principles and shared care within the RAS, they were not always accorded due importance or given due prominence by the teams.

Educational activities occurred in diverse settings and with various audiences, as the exchange of information and expertise was essential for fostering empowerment and accountability in health care. Waiting rooms, operative groups, discussion circles, and community events provided opportune moments to share knowledge and exchange information with health unit users. Moreover, from this perspective, permanent education constituted a routine and highly valuable activity, as it tended to value existing work situations and their outcomes, problematizing processes within the work context, and generating new knowledge among professionals from health units and the municipal basic care network.

The residency's theoretical component comprised transversal and specific axes, with a weekly theoretical content workload of 12 hours, including 6 hours for the transversal axis and 6 hours for the specific axis. Although the residency was not affiliated with an educational institution, it maintained partnerships with municipal institutions, both public and private. Faculty members and representatives from these

institutions were available to teach the modules and foster discussions on public health and physiotherapy within its specific axis.

Discussion

The discussion of this study is organized into four main topics that address different aspects of the physiotherapist's practice in PHC and RMS. The first topic analyzes the role of the physiotherapist in PHC, highlighting the importance of their training, integration with health teams, and the challenges of academic health education in Brazil, in addition to the potential of residency as a strategy to promote interprofessional practice. The second topic focuses on the practical experience of residents in RMS, discussing the challenges and achievements, such as resistance to rehabilitation and the difficulty in organizing operative groups. The third topic addresses the (dis)organization and operationalization of the training process, highlighting the lack of clear flows for residents' integration, the disconnection among those involved, and the absence of adequate planning that would foster a more integrated training. The fourth topic examines the (un)preparedness of preceptors, evidencing the difficulties encountered in communication, understanding the preceptor's role, and executing pedagogical activities.

- Physiotherapy and Primary Health Care

Physiotherapists possess the necessary competencies to act effectively in the SUS's primary care, particularly within the ESF. Their collaboration directly improves the health and quality of life of the population. Furthermore, physiotherapists serve as the first point of contact with users and, when necessary, can refer them to specialized services within the healthcare network or to other intersectoral areas (Queiroz *et al.*, 2022).

Health education, however, represents a significant challenge for altering the healthcare model in Brazil (Torres *et al.*, 2019). Undergraduate physiotherapy curricula, for instance, still insufficiently address crucial topics such as public policies, public

health, intersectoral practice, health education, care management, and primary health care. These areas are fundamental for physiotherapists' training, ensuring their efficient integration into various levels of health care, and enhancing their contribution to the health system (Queiroz *et al.*, 2022).

In this context, Freitas and collaborators (2024) point out that residency provides a favorable environment for physiotherapists' initial contact with PHC. This proximity brings them closer to professionals from other categories and to service users, thereby enhancing comprehensive care strategies and fostering the development of expanded clinical practice.

- Physiotherapeutic Practice within the Multiprofessional Residency in Family Health

Historically, physiotherapeutic practice has been characterized by a technical and rehabilitative approach, often focusing on injured structures and latent painful conditions. This raises the question of the physiotherapist's role "in a small health clinic." The National Primary Care Policy (PNAB) defines Primary Care as the preferred entry point to the SUS, demanding high resolvability, clinical and care capacity, and effective articulation with other points of the RAS (Brasil, 2017).

Upon entering the Family Health Residency, there is an expectation to primarily engage in prevention and health promotion activities. Nevertheless, Primary Care encompasses individual, family, and collective actions aimed at promoting prevention, protection, health promotion, diagnosis, rehabilitation, harm reduction, palliative care, and health surveillance (Brasil, 2017).

The resident's first year of integration into the practical work setting was somewhat disordered. A division of actions between the multiprofessional team and the basic team contradicted the concept of teamwork. Consequently, the resident often found herself reliant on the relationships established by already active professionals in the network, despite the program's coordination requiring collaborative work.

Furthermore, activities and actions carried out by the multiprofessional team were substantially oriented towards the collective, with a generalist and less specific approach. Physiotherapeutic GOs were widely accepted by the community and proved

important for continuous care. However, a deliberate directive from professionals channeled all clinical cases to the physiotherapy operative group, hindering problem resolution and generating user frustration.

Professional resistance is also observed regarding activities proposed by the PNAB, particularly concerning rehabilitation within the ESF units. Physiotherapeutic rehabilitation did not occur in an organized manner; although demands existed, these were directed to non-specific operative groups or referred to the secondary sector. Despite these difficulties, residents successfully implemented individual physiotherapeutic rehabilitation in the health units, supported by patient adherence, positive outcomes, and the assistance of other residents from different areas of practice.

- (Dis)organization and Operationalization of the Training Process in Residency

A primary objective of a residency program is to educate and train health professionals through the integration of teaching, service, and community. This promotes the specialization of professionals through activities that encourage excellent practice centered on comprehensive health care. The focus is to provide a holistic and expanded perspective on users' quality of life, alongside a commitment to understanding the health-disease-care process (Bernardo *et al.*, 2020).

Throughout the observational trajectory, the absence of clear flows for residents' integration into different levels of health care was noted. Although the setting is a practical field designated for the Multiprofessional Residency Program in Primary Care (PRMAB), a gap persists in planning, evaluation, and monitoring mechanisms that adequately support the activities and functions of residents, preceptors, tutors, and COREMU, the program's general coordination.

Even though departments directly linked to the PRMAB exist with responsibilities for deliberations and agreements within the RAS, a disconnection, or in some cases, a weakened connection, among these actors and the residency is evident. This articulation failure negatively impacts residents' training, compromising the

development of essential competencies for their qualified and integrated practice within the health system.

Therefore, the organization and planning process of institutions responsible for the PRMAB must be carefully structured in accordance with ethical and legal principles. Furthermore, adequate training for all involved in the RMS, as well as the active and committed participation of all social agents (Silva, 2017), is crucial. This joint effort aims to develop proposals and consolidate work processes that promote a comprehensive and interdisciplinary experience in practical settings, fostering a truly inter- and multidisciplinary approach (Brasil, 2009).

The observed reality, however, extends far beyond idealized representations or media portrayals. The high turnover of managers and professionals with temporary contracts weakens the RMS, as the actors involved in practical settings are contracted professionals working within the municipality. Moreover, professional relationships and work dynamics often prove unsatisfactory, exhibiting limitations in resolvability and low permeability for the joint development of effective proposals and actions. Such a scenario is reflected in practice, daily evidencing a fragile efficiency in the legacy left in various sectors of activity.

The integration of RMS into health services faces structural and procedural disruptions, such as the high turnover of managers and professionals with political ties. These individuals frequently leave their positions due to shifts in political alliances, influencing agreements and requiring constant (re)adjustments (Pinto; Cyrino, 2014).

- (Un)preparedness of Preceptors in the Training Process

The preceptor plays a fundamental role in residency programs, acting as a central agent in the continuous and mutual knowledge construction process. This role demands not only expertise and technical-practical skills but also a reflective and guiding posture. This is essential for monitoring the resident's technical and humanized training, particularly in primary health care (Carvalho; Gutiérrez, 2021; Maroja; Almeida Júnior; Noronha, 2019; Rodrigues; Witt, 2022).

Thus, it is essential that preceptors remain constantly updated, expanding their theoretical and practical knowledge to inform their practices and discussions. Preceptors' continuous update directly contributes to their ability to identify and overcome inherent challenges in professional training in the health field, in addition to providing the necessary knowledge to address the principles of the teaching-learning process in frequently challenging scenarios (Souza; Ferreira, 2019).

Preceptors' role is relevant in in-service training and in building ties with the community, as they play an essential role in mediating the integration between the resident and the health service. The continuous qualification of preceptors in the training process directly impacts the quality of critical-reflective discussions with residents and contributes to improving practices in various operational settings (Delfino; Vinadé, 2024).

However, preceptors face vulnerability and insufficient communication among preceptors, residents, management, and residency coordination, indicating a disconnection that directly impacts the training process. From this perspective, a gap also exists in preceptors' understanding of their roles and the influence they exert on residents' trajectories, coupled with a lack of transparency in the planning of pedagogical activities.

Throughout the residency period, a diversity in the modes of practice and interaction of each preceptor with the institutional and relational context was noted. This reflects the need to improve the organization of knowledge, interprofessional articulation, and the alignment of objectives and work processes. This observation highlights an urgency in communicational and organizational restructuring, aiming to build a more cohesive and oriented training practice.

Another relevant obstacle is the feeling, frequently observed among preceptors, of outsourcing work. This perception reveals a possible distortion in understanding the RMS proposal. Such a fragmented understanding often prevents preceptors from recognizing their essential role in the construction of the residency's educational project.

Moreover, it is observed that, from the first year, many residents often assume responsibilities in uncovered territories, lacking a support network, and are treated as

permanent staff in the sector. This practice, however, directly contradicts principles established by internal regulations and the political-pedagogical plan, leading residents to constant reflection and questioning about their true role within the residency. More concerning still is that such practices are frequently legitimized by seemingly horizontal dialogues from influential figures, whose generalized ideas often reveal a lack of in-depth knowledge about multiprofessional residency.

Solano (2020) reports that various institutions, including state or municipal health secretariats, frequently integrate residents into service to exploit them as "cheap labor." This trend compromises residents' training by detaching them from the true purpose of RMS — in-service training within and for the SUS — thereby distorting formative objectives in favor of operational demands.

Oliveira, Cavalcante e Pinto (2023) highlight that the public scenario presents considerable structural challenges. These include the presence of many professionals who lack technical skills and humanized training. A scarcity of truly engaged professionals willing to undertake preceptorship in a responsible and qualified manner is also observed.

This irregularity necessitates a strategic approach involving raising awareness among the various actors involved. This can be achieved through the creation of permanent spaces that encourage continuous debate, recognizing that communication and understanding of this process are crucial elements for success in teaching-learning, as well as in planning and decision-making within services (Oliveira; Cavalcante; Pinto, 2023).

Assuming the role of preceptorship within health management contexts presents significant challenges. These include the precariousness of employment ties, structural weaknesses that compromise professional stability, the overload of caregiving duties, and the recurring undervaluation of preceptorship activities. Additionally, there is a scarcity of incentives for continuing and permanent professional training. The absence of managers capable of recognizing and measuring the impact of these gaps severely limits the strengthening of those who should benefit and be supported.

Final Considerations

This experience report demonstrated that RMS are an enabling tool for the physiotherapist's training and practice, integrating them into a multiprofessional context from a PHC perspective. Despite this, the experience highlighted significant challenges. The entire process unfolded within a healthcare system already fraught with difficulties and gaps, including issues of municipal management, inadequate infrastructure, political interference, and, consequently, suboptimal healthcare delivery.

A noteworthy observation was the lack of appreciation and prioritization of the RMS within the municipality, which undermines its vital role as an agent of change, re-shaping, and transformation in health. Federal investment, aiming to support improvements in service provision, professional qualification, and more effective care, faces significant obstacles. These challenges hinder the achievement of RMS objectives, thereby negatively impacting the health of the population.

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